
D4.21 Report from thematic meeting III

WP4

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: DTU, SSI, INRAE, ISS and IP

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Table of contents

1. Background.....	4
2. Program	5
3. Objective	6
4. Content	6
5. Evaluation	8
6. Attendance list	10

D4.21 REPORT FROM THEMATIC MEETING III

1. Background

WP4 is responsible (task 4.3 – subtask 4.3.3) for arranging annual thematic integrative meetings (TIMs) between Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and/or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs). The aim is to facilitate integration across domains, but within themes, addressing specific thematic integrative needs and opportunities. In 2019, the first TIM was arranged in conjunction with the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting on the topic *“Data management and digital innovation”*. The second TIM was held as a webinar in April 2020 on the topic *“Practical use of NGS”*. This year the two JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP were asked to set up a workshop together. As a result the third TIM was held as an online workshop on May 21, 2021 on the subject *“EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective”*.

Subject: EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective

Theme: Reference materials, proficiency testing and laboratory protocols

Venue: Microsoft Teams TC

Organisers: Rene S. Hendriksen, DTU (rshe@food.dtu.dk) and Nadia Boisen, SSI (nbo@ssi.dk) with support from OHEJP WP4 (othejp@sva.se)

Target groups: Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects, Stakeholders and EURLs

Number of participants: 93

A Save the Date was created and distributed by the OHEJP Comms Team to the OHEJP Programme Management Team (PMT), Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and JIP/JRP Project Leaders on April 15, 2021. The Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA were also informed about and invited to the workshop. The invitation together with the agenda and the meeting link was sent out on May 10, 2021.

2. Program

09.30-09.35 Welcome

René Hendriksen, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, DTU

09.35-09.45 Surveillance, methodologies, quality assessments and provision of reference material: A One Health perspective

Flemming Scheutz, Statens Serum Institut, SSI

09.45-09.55 The importance of harmonised protocols and the description of One Health microbiological system: An overview of OH-Harmony-Cap

Nadia Boisen, Statens Serum Institut, SSI

09.55-10.05 The importance of reference materials and proficiency: An overview of CARE

René Hendriksen, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, DTU

10.05-10.25 New methods and adaptability: principles and experiences on pros and cons in the introduction/changes of laboratory methods

Rosangela Tozzoli, Istituto superiore di sanità, ISS

10.25-10.40 Validation criteria of microbiological Reference Materials (RM) and role of Biological Resource Centers (BRC) for their conservation and dissemination

Michel-Yves Mistou, National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment, INRAE

10.40-10.50 Break

10.50-11.10 How to cope with Nagoya and dual-use regulations when you set up a collection of bacterial reference materials?

Olivier Chesneau, Institut Pasteur, IP

11.10-11.25 Innovative genomic proficiency testing methods

Jeppe Boel, Statens Serum Institut, SSI

11.25-11.45 OHEJP activities and outputs: How will they be translated in to One Health practice?

Panel:

Mirko Rossi, EFSA

Johanna Takkinen, ECDC

11.45-12.00 Q&A Session

3. Objective

The workshop aimed to bring OHEJP project members together to discuss the importance of reference materials, proficiency testing and harmonised laboratory protocols. Encouraging discussion between specialists in different fields was a key objective.

4. Content

Flemming Scheutz's presentation focused on four different fields: 1) The ISO standardisation in the food sector; 2) The challenges in the field of diagnostics within the public health sector posed by the increased use of commercial diagnostic kits and gastrointestinal panels; 3) Possible consequences of the out-phasing of the use of zink in pig production; 4) External quality assessment (EQA) programmes: Specification of test performance and requirements for methods are needed across the One Health sector.

Nadia Boisen summarised the OH-Harmony-CAP project. The project aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe. Furthermore, the provision of a quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and suggest future studies on how to best detect and characterise food borne pathogens across the OH sectors. In particular, the development of a first of a kind OHLabCap and survey, targeting food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes, was emphasised.

René Hendriksen's presentation started with an introduction of CARE followed by the objectives linking the project to the Integrative Strategy Matrix. The CARE partner institutes as well as the Work packages (WP) were presented, including the major tasks of each WP and the current status of the work.

Rosangela Tozzoli's presentation focused on the issues linked to the development of new methods, especially when proposing changes to existing methods. In particular, the speaker reported on the EURL for *E. coli* experience on the assessment of the method's performance through the organization of Inter-laboratory studies (ILS), thanks to the support of National Reference Laboratories for *E. coli*. The organization of ILS together with the high participation of NRLs, has been extremely useful for the determination of performance parameters of the standard method for the detection of STEC in food (ISO/TS 13136) and fine-tuning protocols (including the ongoing revision of the ISO standard of STEC detection in food).

Michel-Yves Mistou's presentation included:

- An introduction to, inventory of and selection of Microbiological Reference materials in the CARE context
- How to make the EUROpanelOH visible
- The CARE EUROpanelOH database and website
- An introduction to the concept of Biological Resource Centers (BRCs)
- Missions of BRCs and their specific QMS
- Dissemination of EUROpanelOH RMs through BRCs

- Sustainability of the EUROpanelOH
- BRC's are assets, let's use them!

Olivier Chesneau talked about the necessity to comply with European regulations and updates (*EU regulation 511/2014 for the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) and Annex I of Council regulation 428/2009 for the list of dual-use bacteria*). The speaker suggested to visit the ABS clearing house (<https://absch.cbd.int>) for useful information on the National ABS landscape (legislation, administration, policy issues and contact point officers) for the country where the sampling has been done. Furthermore, it is wise to consult the [Volume II of the Australia Group Common Control List](#) handbooks to get basic descriptions of and information on the notable features, packaging and typical ill-intentioned applications.

Jepp Boel's presentation focused on the development of new proficiency testing (PT), methods and external quality assessment (EQA) schemes that are needed to assess the combined performance of the OH sector, i.e. the human, food/feed, and veterinary sectors. The three pilot PTs that are conducted in the CARE project were presented: 1) Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens; 2) Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS, and 3) Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data. Different aspects, including practical information about the pilots and the idea of developing a guidance document on how to organise future OH EQA schemes were also presented.

The webinar was recorded and is available [here](#) (If the link does not work, try to copy/paste it.).

5. Evaluation

The interest for the thematic integrative meetings seems to increase. The combination of reference materials and laboratory protocols was appreciated and provided different perspectives, giving participants with different backgrounds openings for raising their questions. The update on the Nagoya regulations was of particular interest to the scientists. Giving the participants the possibility to write their questions in the chat for the moderator/speakers to read and comment on was a good concept for handling the discussion, since there were lots of questions for each speaker. The meeting concluded with a panel discussion with representatives from ECDC (Johanna Takkinen) and EFSA (Valentina Rizzi and Mirko Rossi). Providing additional time for the panel discussion between the representatives from ECDC and EFSA could have been beneficial.

In general the Teams format worked well, even if some participants had some initial issues with accessing the meeting. These issues were quickly solved and in general the format worked without problems. The only drawback noted was the difficulty to make a complete attendance list as not all participants used their full names nor mentioned their affiliations. even though they were asked to provide this information in the beginning of the meeting and reminded later in the chat function.

Comments from speakers Flemming Scheutz, Nadia Boisen and Rosangela Tozzoli

In general there was a huge interest in the initiative of providing RM, but also in the database enabling easy access. It was discussed how much data will be necessary to provide.

The need for a more integrative One Health approach in organizing external quality assurance (EQA) schemes was commented. There is a need to test the quality of both genomic data generated and the application of bioinformatic pipelines. It was also discussed to share the EQA data as reference material (RM) for future benchmarking etc.

The launch of several risk assessment surveys was commented including how to improve the availability and the quality of the existing data relevant for risk assessment.

The cost of shipment for BSL-3 bacteria (*STEC* and *Salmonella typhi* are among the seven pathogens selected by CARE) is very high. There is no GDPR information in the CARE database.

A set of questions, as agreed by CARE and OH-Harmony-Cap, were sent to the panel in advance:

1. Do ECDC, EFSA and the Commission see the outcome of the Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) as a part of an EU strategy going forward?
2. What are the plans for OH networks on the organisms that are targeted in OH-HARMONY-CAP and CARE?
3. In general, how do we further coordinate with WHO and FAO?
4. How will ECDC, EFSA and the Commission use the output from the JIPs? Are there any plans for sustainability?
5. Does the EU have plans to develop a bacterial/parasitological analytic manual for diagnostics? If so, will it be done in a OH environment?

There was a wide agreement that there is a need for a continuation of the activities performed in the JIPs and the implementation of outcomes should go beyond dissemination. Specific actions could be considered such as implementation projects, including developing electronic support systems, training sessions and on-site guidance. The OH-Harmony-Cap WP5 is dedicated to the dissemination of results and very aware of the need for sustainability measures.

OHEJP activities and outputs: How will they be translated into OH practice?

ECDC has postponed the preparation of the One Health strategy due to COVID-19. In the past years, possibilities for collaboration with the EURLs in the EQA schemes have been sought and selected joint rounds have been performed for *Listeria monocytogenes* and STEC including antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* isolates.

EFSA gave a written feedback to the question before the meeting:

“In general, the position of EFSA related to the JIPs is to follow the development of the projects, and, when possible, to collaborate with the members of the project in order to identify synergies, avoid divergences and facilitate the smooth integration of projects’ outputs with ongoing and future processes in EFSA, if applicable.

Within EFSA’s remit, we will ensure to always consider the development done at MS level or EU level for our future activities. One example is the development of a system in EFSA for the collection of WGS data to support outbreak detection and investigation. A different example, is the work done with ORION that was recently posted on the research community or to the recent Editorial on OneHealth: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.e190501>.*

For your information, EFSA’s work is mainly undertaken in response to specific requests from the European Commission, European Parliament and EU Member States.

With regard to your request, we are not in position to answer questions related to EU strategies regarding the future coordination of JIPs and the use and sustainability of their outputs. The decisions on the EU strategy are under the remit of the European Commission and the European Parliament.

We can only foresee that at the end of the JIPs, the European Commission will evaluate the outcomes of these JIPs and, if it considers relevant, it will mandate EFSA to answer specific questions using the instrument provided by JIPs or to implement eventually systems developed by the JIPs.”

**Please, contact EFSA for more information, as you need credentials to access the research community.*

6. Attendance list*

Speakers

René S. Hendriksen, DTU
Nadia Boisen, SSI
Flemming Scheutz, SSI
Rosangela Tozzoli, ISS
Michel-Yves Mistou, INRAE
Olivier Chesneau, IP
Jeppe Boel, SSI

OHEJP administration

Karin Artursson, WP4 leader, SVA
Annemarie Käsbohrer, WP5 leader, BfR
Roberto La Ragione, WP6 leader, UoS
Dolores Gavier-Widén, WP7 deputy leader, SVA
Pikka Jokelainen, WP3/WP5 deputy leader, SSI
Lena Tuominen, WP4 collaborator, SVA
Jade Passey, Comms Team, UoS
Ludovico Sepe, WP5 collaborator, BfR
Lucia de Juan Ferre, WP2 deputy leader, UCM

Other participants

Elina Lahti, SVA
Antonio Battisti
Roderick Card, APHA
Sibel Kizil
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Anne Margrete Urdahl, NVI
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Stephan Bronzwaer, EFSA
Valentina Rizzi, EFSA
Mélanie Gay, ANSES
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Lin Cathrine T. Brandal, NIPH
Elke Burow, BfR
Catarina Flink
Mónica Oleastro
Cecilia Jernberg, ECDC
Patricia Alba
Rune Stensvold, SSI
Virginia Carfora
Gudrun Overesch, VETSUISSE
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Ben Wit
Camilla Sekse, NVI
Patrizia Rossi, ISS
Cristina Belo Correia
Jacinto Gomes, INIAV
Cristina de Frutos
Vicente Lopez
Robert Söderlund, SVA
Margarida Pires Simões
Sara Savić

** some participants represented several projects*